

Research paper

Classification of the difficulty of a climbing route using the transformation of representation spaces and cascading classifier ensemble (CCE)

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ABSTRACT

Climbing has gained popularity in recent years and encompasses various disciplines, among which bouldering stands out as one of the most well-known. Determining the difficulty of a bouldering route is a challenging task due to the varying combinations of handholds. Accurate assessment of the difficulty of a route is important, as it allows a climber's ability to be measured against that of other climbers. Furthermore, climbers must gradually progress from less to more difficult routes to improve their skills effectively. The difficulty rating of a route poses a complex problem, and previous research has explored machine learning techniques, including deep learning, to address it. We propose a novel approach based on a series of transformations in the representation space that incorporates expert knowledge to improve the classification of climbing route difficulty. We introduce a cascade classifier ensemble (CCE) model specifically designed for levelling classification. Compared to similar works, this model also incorporates explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) mechanisms. With the CEE model, the relevance of specific handholds in the transition from one level of difficulty to the next is obtained. Finally, we illustrate how our proposed model not only achieves good results but also empowers climbers to identify the most crucial sections in each level of difficulty.

1. Introduction

Climbing is a sport in which climbers scale vertical walls, either in natural rock formations or artificial walls known as climbing walls. The objective is to reach the summit by following predefined routes without falling. Climbing walls consist of sequences of handholds that form climbing routes. Bouldering is a form of rock climbing that involves climbing short, challenging routes, typically without the use of ropes or harnesses, and often focuses on strength, technique, and problem-solving skills. It is derived from mountaineering and initially served as a form of training for mountaineers during the off-season.

Currently, the difficulty of climbing routes is measured using a preestablished grading system. There are many different metric grading systems around the world (Corrigan, 2015). In recent years, efforts have been made to homogenize these systems. The most relevant approach has been carried out by the International Rock Climbing Research Association (IRCRA), where a consensus has been reached on the conversion between grading systems (Draper et al., 2015). Currently, in Europe, the most popular boulder classification system is the Fontainebleau grading system (Font scale), which consists of

one, two, or three characters to represent the overall difficulty of the route. A number from 3 to 9 is accompanied by a letter from 'A' to 'C' (not always present) and a plus sign + (not always present). Thus, a combination of a higher number and letter and the presence of the plus sign indicate a more difficult climbing route, as shown in Table 1 (e.g., 6A+ is more difficult than 6A but easier than 6B). The most difficult boulder route climbed to date is 9A.

Climbing routes are initially graded by the first person to climb them, and a consensus is reached as subsequent climbers repeat the routes. This system is subjective and multivariate, with the objective of determining whether a route falls within an acceptable difficulty margin for climbers. Grading allows the difficulty of bouldering problems to be quantified, thus enabling the ability of a climber to be measured against that of other climbers.

The MoonBoard, a standardized climbing wall, plays a significant role in this study. It is 2.44 m wide and 3.15 m high and inclined at a 40-degree angle with a variety of handholds. The MoonBoard maintains consistent dimensions, handhold placements, and angles worldwide. It comprises 18 rows (numbered 1 to 18) and 11 columns (labelled A to

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Fig. 1. The 2016 MoonBoard is an illuminated board with a Bluetooth-enabled mobile phone app that connects the user to a database of climbing routes.

Table 1
The Fontainebleau scale grading system.

3	4	4+	5	5+	6A	6A+	6B	6B+	6C	6C+	7A
7A+	7B	7B+	7C	7C+	8A	8A+	8B	8B+	8C	8C+	9A

K), ensuring that a specific handhold, such as G9, remains identical across all locations. This study focuses on the 2016 version of the MoonBoard (see Fig. 1).

A MoonBoard route is described by handholds marked with a round circle, indicating the holds that can be used. The start and end handholds are denoted by green and red circles, respectively (see Fig. 2).

Classifying the difficulty of a MoonBoard route based on a given configuration remains an ongoing challenge. Given the increasing popularity of climbing as a sport, it is desirable that climbers have a means of assessing the difficulty of a route. This assessment would facilitate gradual skill development from less complex to more challenging routes. Our proposed model represents an advancement in climbing route classification models. As detailed in subsequent sections, the new approach integrates explainable AI (XAI) mechanisms. Consequently, it provides not only a more precise indication of a route’s difficulty level but also information about the most relevant handholds influencing its classification at a specific difficulty level. This insight into the importance of handholds enables the climber to identify the most challenging sections, optimize their body positioning, and efficiently manage the effort required to overcome these segments.

Previous research in the scientific field has explored symbolic and machine learning approaches to this problem (Kempen, 2018; Dobles et al., 2017; Tai et al., 2020; Duh and Chang, 2021). However, these classifiers are subjective because they learn from human classifications. The objective of a climbing route classifier is to achieve the reliability of a human classifier. However, the reliability of human classifiers is somewhat limited, as will be discussed later. Therefore, this work aims to evaluate the following hypotheses:

1. The introduction of expert knowledge is expected to improve the reliability of route classifiers. To this end, a pipeline based on representation space transformations is proposed, allowing for the integration of expert knowledge.

Fig. 2. Description of a MoonBoard 2016 route. Only handholds with circles can be used. The start and end handholds are shown in green and red, respectively.

2. This research focuses on a collaborative environment in which climbers can contribute to climbing route ratings. Introducing a new rating would typically require retraining the classifier with all historical ratings, along with the new rating. In this study, a new cascade classifier architecture is presented that minimizes the burden of retraining.
3. The proposal provides XAI mechanisms. The aim of the new model is to identify the relevance of each handhold to be able to progress from one level of difficulty to a higher one.

To validate the models designed in this study, a dataset obtained from the official MoonBoard website (MoonBoard, 2023) is utilized. This dataset comprises 30,634 graded climbing routes, ranging from level 6B+ to level 8B+, using the French grading system (Fontainebleau). The size of this dataset provides sufficient resources to validate the proposed innovations.

The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows. First, an overview of recent research on calculating climbing route difficulty is presented. Next, the pipeline of representation space transformations and the novel cascade classifier ensemble (CCE) architecture are described. Subsequently, the results of the experiments conducted using this representation and ensemble classifier are presented. Finally, the paper concludes with a summary of the findings and suggestions for future research.

2. Related works

In recent years, the evaluation of climbing technique through the use of technology has attracted significant interest, mainly due to the acceptance of climbing as an Olympic sport in Tokyo 2020. Most related work has focused on the analysis of climbing styles in speed climbing (Elias et al., 2021; Pandurevic et al., 2023).

In recent years, wearable devices have begun to be used in climbing. Their uses have varied and include estimating climber fatigue (Galluzzi

Table 2

Accuracy of the four climbers in the experiment. We present the exact results, as well as those in which only one grading error is made.

	Exact Grade	Grade with 1 error
Expert climber 1	0.38	0.79
Expert climber 2	0.42	0.82
Novice climber 1	0.23	0.45
Novice climber 2	0.18	0.25

et al., 2020), detecting climber falls (Bonfitto et al., 2019), and guiding training routes (Kosmalla et al., 2016a,b).

However, wearables have not been used to classify the difficulty of climbing routes. In this regard, few studies on this topic have been conducted. In Kalyanaraman et al. (2015), IMU and EMG sensors and barometers are used to track a climber's movements on a route. This information has a statistical purpose but is not used to classify the difficulty of the route. In Ebert et al. (2018), the researchers use a set of accelerometers located on the climber's body.

Another technology of interest for analysing effort and style is computer vision-based systems. A dataset that integrates multimodal information (RGB cameras, LiDAR, and IMUs) to represent a climber's movements has recently been published (Yan et al., 2023). In Elias et al. (2021) and Beltrán Beltrán et al. (2023), video cameras were used to obtain the skeleton of a climber. The climber's skeleton is used to evaluate the possible errors made to improve their climbing style and, consequently, their performance (focusing on Olympic speed climbing).

Other work on classifying the difficulty of a climbing route is based on the representation of the route on a standardized platform (the MoonBoard platform). To understand the complexity of route difficulty classification, an experiment was conducted to estimate the human-level performance of MoonBoard route classification. In this way, we were able to compare the performance of the models proposed in our work against that of a human classifier. The experiment involved four climbers: two expert climbers who had more than ten years of climbing experience, had climbed routes with a difficulty of 8A and were sport climbing technicians (TD2); and two amateur climbers, who had fewer than ten years of climbing experience, specifically, five and eight years, and had climbed routes with a maximum grade of 7A+.

In this experiment, participants were asked to grade ten climbing routes on the MoonBoard only by observing valid handholds for them. The proportion of correct answers for each participant was recorded, as well as the proportion of correct answers if a degree of difference error was allowed. For example, if the actual grade of the block was 6B+ and our participants graded it as 6C or 6B, their answers were considered valid. The ten routes utilized in our study were specifically selected from MoonBoard Benchmark Boulders. The selection process involved applying a "benchmark" filter and subsequently sorting the routes based on their "rating". This meticulous procedure was implemented to guarantee the inclusion of the most representative climbing routes for each grade.

Table 2 shows the results of the experiment. The highest success rate is achieved by Expert Climber 2, with a 0.42 accuracy rate in terms of exact hits and a 0.82 accuracy rate when allowing a degree of error. On the other hand, the worst results were obtained by Novice Climber 2, who had only 5 years of climbing experience and who obtained a 0.18 accuracy rate and a 0.35 accuracy rate when allowing one degree of error.

The use of the MoonBoard as a standard system for determining route difficulty in studies does not rely on wearables and is a less intrusive technique. Similarly, computer vision-based systems aim to analyse climbers' movements to improve their climbing style and their performance (mainly in relation to Olympic speed climbing). Additionally, previous work measures the difficulty of a route after the climber has completed it (*a posteriori*). Our aim is to obtain a system that, when faced with a route configuration, determines its difficulty (*a priori*).

Table 3

Results obtained in Tai et al. (2020) for the difficulty rating of climbing routes on the MoonBoard.

Model	f1_score	Auc
SVM	0.29	0.66
MLP	0.22	0.66
Random Forest	0.28	0.67
GCN (L) 2S, MH, PMI	0.29	0.72
GCN (L) 4S, MH, PMI	0.31	0.73

Table 4

Results obtained in Dobles et al. (2017) for the difficulty rating of climbing routes on the MoonBoard.

Model	Accuracy
Naive Bayes	0.34
Softmax	0.365
CNN	0.34

In Tai et al. (2020), the authors used graph neural networks (GNNs) to classify the difficulty of a MoonBoard route. They compare the results obtained with GNNs against other algorithms, such as random forest, multilayer perceptron (MLP) or support vector machines (SVMs). To encode the routes, they use both one-hot and multihot encoding. The authors conclude that the GNN with four convolutional steps obtained the best results of the other proposed models. The best of their results has an f1_score of 0.31 (see Table 3).

Dobles et al. (2017) propose classifying the difficulty of a route on the MoonBoard by applying three machine learning algorithms: naive Bayes, softmax regression and a convolutional neural network (CNN). To represent a route, which is the input to these algorithms, they directly map the handholds of the route. In this way, they obtain a matrix of dimensions 18×11 with values of 0 if the handhold is not used and 1 if it is used. For the first two models, this matrix is flattened, while for the last model, the data are used as input for a two-dimensional matrix. The authors conclude that all three models have comparable accuracy, although they mention that the convolutional neural network generates better results than the other two models. The results reach an accuracy of 0.365 (see Table 4).

Previous studies have commonly employed an input array of 1s and 0s to denote the presence or absence of handholds in a given route. In particular, in Duh and Chang (2021), a novel preprocessing technique named BetaMove is introduced, which aims to represent a route through a sequence of hand movements, mimicking human-like behaviour during climbing. Following this sequence encoding, the authors leverage a recurrent neural network (RNN) for route difficulty classification. This approach, which incorporates human-like route representation, yields results that closely align with human performance. Subsequently, in Stapel (2023), the BetaMove representation was refined by introducing local outlier probabilities (LoOPs). An ordinal regression model is then employed as a classifier, in which a route is deconstructed into a series of individual moves. The difficulty of each move is evaluated, and the evaluations are aggregated to determine the overall difficulty of the route.

Significantly, our work deviates substantially from these proposals. First, our MoonBoard configuration preprocessing differs, albeit it starts with the BetaMove representation. In our approach, moreover, we augment this representation with expert knowledge. The difficulty of a route depends on several factors, including movement dynamics, wall angle, and climb length. The intricacies of the movement include considerations such as spatial relationships, the orientation between the handholds, and the type of handhold. We introduce a preprocessing step involving the transformation of the representation space, wherein expert-based knowledge is incorporated. As elucidated in subsequent sections, information pertaining to the difficulty levels of handholds is integrated into our model.

Additionally, our approach is distinguished through the integration of XAI mechanisms. In the realm of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly in machine learning (ML), there is a pronounced interest in enhancing the explainability of models. XAI encompasses a suite of processes and methodologies designed to enable users to comprehend and trust the results generated by ML models. As computational capabilities have advanced, more sophisticated models have emerged. However, with these models, it becomes challenging for individuals to comprehend and trace the decision-making process leading to a specific result. These models are often referred to as “black-box” models, as they are constructed purely from data. In the context of highly reliable yet opaque models, data scientists struggle to decipher or elucidate the rationale behind specific ML model outcomes.

Numerous recent publications in the domain of XAI, such as Schwalbe and Finzel (2023), Vassiliades et al. (2021), Dwivedi et al. (2023), Saeed and Omlin (2023) and Barredo Arrieta et al. (2020), span various industries, including but not limited to health (Nazir et al., 2023; Chaddad et al., 2023), smart cities (Javed et al., 2023), and cybersecurity (Capuano et al., 2022). Our proposed model surpasses the conventional task of merely indicating the difficulty level of a route. Furthermore, we provide climbers with detailed insights into the significance of each handhold within a route, facilitating a smooth transition from one difficulty level to a higher one. This augmentation enables climbers to strategically focus on refining their movement resolution skills based on the specific relevance of handholds. The incorporation of XAI mechanisms is pivotal for achieving this enhanced interpretability within our proposed model.

The purpose of our study is threefold. First, we investigate whether improving the representation of routes with expert information can improve the reliability of route classifiers. Second, we address the inherently collaborative nature of these systems. Typically, a route classifier is integrated within a mobile application based on which climbers can access information regarding the difficulty of a route. Within this collaborative environment, climbers can contribute their ratings for completed climbing routes. The inclusion of new ratings enriches the existing corpus of ratings within the system. Incorporating these new ratings into the classifier’s modelling requires undertaking the learning process with all historical ratings, in addition to the new rating. To mitigate this impact, we present a new cascade classifier architecture designed to minimize the associated computational burden. Finally, owing to the cascading nature of the proposed classifier, we develop an explanatory framework that elucidates the factors contributing to the classification of a route as having a specific degree of difficulty.

2.1. Dataset

The dataset is obtained from MoonBoard’s official website (MoonBoard, 2023), which hosts a database with all climbing routes that have ever been uploaded by users of their application. Thus, Je-Rui Chang and Yi-Shiou Duh were able to use a webscraping script to obtain a total of 30634 climbing routes. This dataset can be obtained from their public repository (Chang, 2021). In our study, we adhere to a rationale similar to that outlined in Duh and Chang (2021) in Section “4 Dataset and Features”.

The dataset is composed of a total of 30634 climbing routes with grades ranging from 6B+ to 8B+. Since any user of the application can publish unrestricted climbing routes, it is necessary to clean the data to filter and obtain the most robust data for our analysis, thus avoiding erroneous data, publications by amateur climbers or routes that are impossible to use.

First, any routes that are not repeated are omitted. Such routes indicate that other users of the application have not been able to corroborate the grade proposed by the first user, and most likely, these data are low quality. Next, routes with errors, namely, those that had too many or too few handholds, too many start and end handholds and poorly graded routes, are eliminated.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the degree of difficulty of routes.

Fig. 3 shows the distribution of the data by degree of difficulty. The distribution of the data is unbalanced, with lower grade routes having more weight. This result is a direct representation of the distribution of climbers today, where a large number of climbers are able to climb easier grade routes, while only a small proportion of climbers are able to climb routes over 7C+.

The aim of the models we build is to estimate the degree of difficulty of a route. As input, we use the result of the pipeline of transformations of the representation space (described in the previous sections). The output of the models is the degree of difficulty of the route. The grade of the climbing routes was transformed into a numerical value by mapping the grade to its equivalent numerical value. In addition, a mapping was conducted to convert between the European (Fontainebleau) and the American (Hueco) grade systems. Thus, the number of classes with the European system is 12, while with the American system, it is 10. Table 5 shows the mapping conducted between the different types of grading systems to make these transformations and their corresponding numerical values.

3. Pipeline of representation space transformations

This section describes the transformations of the representation spaces that are performed to determine the degree of difficulty of a given route on the MoonBoard.

The initial representation (see Fig. 4) corresponds to a matrix of 0 s and 1 s. The handholds on the climbing route are represented as a matrix of 18 rows by 11 columns such that each element of this matrix represents a MoonBoard climbing handhold with a value of 1 if the handhold is grabbed or 0 otherwise. The position (0, 0) of this matrix represents the handhold in the upper left corner of the climbing wall (18A), while position (17, 10) represents the handhold in the lower right corner of the climbing wall.

Fig. 5 shows the pipeline of representation space transformations. Three transformations are performed on the initial representation. More details of each of the transformations will be provided in the following paragraphs, but we would like to draw attention to the last transformation, which is indicated after the dotted line. Up to this dotted line, the transformations were taken from previous work, such as Duh and Chang (2021). The novelty of this pipeline lies in the introduction of the last transformation. As will be shown, this transformation fuses expert knowledge to improve the accuracy of classifying the difficulty of climbing routes. We now describe the three transformations one by one.

The first transformation performed on the initial representation transforms an 18×11 matrix into a one-dimensional vector of 198

Table 5
Equivalence between different grading systems.

Numerical Equivalent	Degree (fontainebleau)	Degree (hueco)	Numerical Equivalent
0	6B+	V4	0
1	6C	V5	1
2	6C+		
3	7A	V6	2
4	7A+	V7	3
5	7B		
6	7B+	V8	4
7	7C	V9	5
8	7C+	V10	6
9	8A	V11	7
10	8A+	V12	8
11	8B	V13	9

Fig. 4. Initial representation space. On the left, a MoonBoard route. On the right, its initial representation.

values (see Fig. 5, transformation T_1). The position (0,0) of this matrix represents the handhold in the upper left corner of the climbing wall (18A), while the position (17, 10) represents the handhold in the lower right corner of the climbing wall.

The second transformation of the representation space starts from a set of vectors with values $\{0, 1\}$. Based on expert knowledge, information about an optimal sequence of movements, very close to what a human climber would perform on the basis of a specific route, is included in the new representation. Specifically, the transformation called “BetaMove” is used (Duh and Chang, 2021). The transformation generates the order of the handholds and which hand has to be used for each handhold of the route. The result is a vector of dimension n with values 1 (if the n th handhold is held with the right hand) or -1 (if the n th handhold is held with the left hand), where n is the handhold number on the route (see Fig. 5).

Finally, the last transformation of the representation space is carried out. This new transformation includes information from the expert related to the difficulty of the hold. Three professional experts assigned the degree of difficulty of the MoonBoard handholds so that 1 is the easiest and 9 is the most difficult. The difficulty rating takes into account characteristics such as size, shape, and granularity. In addition, it is possible that the degree of difficulty depends on the hand with which a handhold is grasped. The allocation for each of the hands and handholds is shown in Table 6, so that the same handhold can have two different scores depending on the hand by which it is grasped (R - Right, L - Left).

An instance of this transformation of the representation space is shown in Fig. 6.

Therefore, a climbing route is represented by a vector of 198 positions. The values that the elements of this vector can take are between -9 and 9 , inclusive, where 0 indicates that this handhold has not been used and a value other than 0 represents that this handhold has been used. Furthermore, if the value is negative, this handhold is grasped with the left hand, while if the value is positive, this handhold is grasped with the right hand.

4. Cascading classifier ensemble (CCE)

The aim of our work is to classify the difficulty of climbing routes. Therefore, it is necessary to use a classifier algorithm that, based on the encoding of a route (previous section), estimates the level of difficulty of that route. When assigning a difficulty level, we must take into account that this categorical variable has an order relation among the labels. If we use a grading system such as the American system (Hueco), the routes can be ranked from V4 (lowest difficulty) to V13 (highest difficulty). This problem is known as “ordinal classification”. It starts from a set of instances composed of a pair of attribute classes $(x, y) \in X \times Y$, where x is a vector belonging to the space of representations X (previous section), and y is a label belonging to an ordered space $Y = \{V4, V5, V6, V7, V8, V9, V10, V11, V12, V13\}$. In this space, there is an order relation between labels expressed by $V4 < V5 < V6 < V7 <$

Fig. 5. Pipeline of applied representation space transformations. Three transformations are described in this section, with the third transformation being novel compared to related works. In this third transformation, expert knowledge is integrated to improve the classification of climbing routes.

Table 6
Difficulty assigned to each hold: (X,Y) position of the hold, R-Right hand, L-Left hand.

X	Y	R	L	X	Y	R	L	X	Y	R	L	X	Y	R	L
0	17	5	5	2	4	5	5	5	8	4	4	8	13	7	3
0	15	2	4	3	17	9	9	5	7	2	2	8	12	3	2
0	14	2	2	3	16	4	4	5	6	3	5	8	11	5	4
0	13	2	7	3	15	3	3	5	5	1	1	8	10	6	6
0	12	4	4	3	14	4	3	5	4	7	8	8	9	6	6
0	11	4	4	3	13	1	2	6	17	8	8	8	8	4	3
0	10	0	1	3	12	3	3	6	16	4	4	8	7	1	0
0	9	1	2	3	11	7	6	6	15	1	1	8	6	3	2
0	8	3	8	3	10	2	5	6	14	3	5	8	5	3	2
0	4	4	4	3	9	5	5	6	13	4	4	8	4	6	6
1	17	9	9	3	8	4	4	6	12	7	7	8	3	6	3
1	15	3	5	3	7	1	1	6	11	5	3	9	15	2	4
1	14	4	4	3	6	3	4	6	10	3	3	9	13	2	3
1	12	3	5	3	5	3	3	6	9	4	3	9	12	4	4
1	11	3	3	3	4	3	2	6	8	6	5	9	11	3	2
1	10	6	7	3	2	3	3	6	7	5	5	9	10	2	2
1	9	6	8	4	17	9	9	6	6	2	1	9	9	5	3
1	8	5	4	4	15	4	4	6	5	4	6	9	8	5	2
1	7	6	6	4	14	6	6	6	3	8	8	9	7	8	8
1	6	3	3	4	13	4	4	6	1	7	7	9	6	5	5
1	5	1	3	4	12	7	7	7	17	4	4	9	5	1	1
1	3	3	6	4	11	7	6	7	15	4	4	9	4	5	5
1	2	6	7	4	10	4	5	7	14	1	1	9	1	6	2
2	17	4	4	4	9	4	6	7	13	5	3	10	17	9	9
2	15	1	1	4	8	3	3	7	12	4	3	10	15	5	5
2	14	2	4	4	7	8	8	7	11	4	4	10	13	4	2
2	13	3	3	4	6	6	6	7	10	7	7	10	12	3	3
2	12	3	8	4	5	3	5	7	9	9	8	10	11	3	3
2	11	4	4	5	15	1	1	7	8	5	6	10	10	6	7
2	10	3	4	5	14	3	4	7	7	5	3	10	9	1	1
2	9	3	7	5	13	3	8	7	6	1	1	10	8	7	7
2	8	2	2	5	12	2	3	7	4	3	6	10	7	3	3
2	7	2	6	5	11	4	4	8	17	6	6	10	6	5	5
2	6	5	5	5	10	6	5	8	15	6	6	10	5	2	2
2	5	1	2	5	9	5	5	8	14	3	3	10	4	9	9

Fig. 6. Transformation of the representation space by introducing information on the difficulty bracket of the handholds ($T_3 : \{0, 1, -1\}^{198} \rightarrow \{-9, -8, -7, -6, -5, -4, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}^{198}$).

$V8 < V9 < V10 < V11 < V12 < V13$, where $<$ describes an order relation.

When faced with a complex classification problem where there are a considerable number of classes, the use of ensemble methods is recommended. An ensemble of classifiers consists of a set of classifiers whose predictions are combined to obtain a final classification result. Its goal is to improve classification performance by combining the predictions of different models. Depending on how the classifiers are combined, there are two main families of algorithms: bagging and boosting. The bagging technique is based on the independent construction of a set of classifiers and produces a final result that combines their predictions. The boosting technique builds classifiers sequentially and tries to reduce the bias of the combined classifier.

In this paper, we present a boosting technique. The main problem of classifying the difficulty of a route has been transformed into n binary classifiers that are trained to determine whether a climbing route has a difficulty level higher than a given route. In our case, we use a scale of difficulty that increases gradually from $V4$ to $V13$. Therefore, we need to build nine binary classifiers.

The first step is to prepare a dataset for each of these nine classifiers. Starting from the initial dataset, nine datasets are built whose dependent variable is 1 if a stay (climbing route) is greater than a given level. For example, for the first classifier (level $V4$) a dataset is built indicating the dependent variable with a 1 if the route has a level higher than $V4$, otherwise, it is indicated with a 0. A dataset is built for each level of the American grading system (Hueco) up to level $V12$. Fig. 7 shows the original dataset at the top. The dataset contains the coding of a route and, as a dependent variable, the complexity of the American grading system. The original dataset is replicated as many times as the number of levels of its grading system (in this case, 9). In these new datasets, the dependent variable is modified to 1 if the climbing route has a higher level than a given route and 0 otherwise.

The new datasets are used to train nine binary classifiers capable of determining whether the difficulty of a climbing route is greater than a given level.

Determining the difficulty level of a climbing route poses an ordinal classification challenge, where misclassification can have serious consequences. This scenario can be generalized to other problems where misclassifying a sample as lower than its actual level carries risks. In the context of climbing, classifying a route as a lower level than it truly is can lead to climber frustration or, in more severe cases, significant injuries. Therefore, it is crucial to adopt a conservative approach when assessing the difficulty of climbing routes.

Our proposed solution involves combining binary classifiers sequentially while applying a conservative policy. The architecture of the cascade of classifiers ensemble (CCE) is depicted in Fig. 8. The process begins with the first binary classifier called the “GreaterThanV4 Model”. This classifier yields two outputs. If the difficulty of the route surpasses

the $V4$ level, the evaluation proceeds to the next binary model, the “GreaterThanV5 Model”. Otherwise, the difficulty label $V4$ is assigned. Each binary model is evaluated successively, and if an affirmative output is obtained, the subsequent binary model is assessed. Otherwise, the label of the current level under evaluation is assigned. If all binary models produce positive outputs, the top-level label ($V13$) is assigned.

Each binary classifier within the system is configured to derive its output, indicating whether the route corresponds to a specific difficulty level or, conversely, exceeds that level. During the training phase for each binary classifier (designated classifier n), only samples of routes with a difficulty level equal to n or surpassing n are incorporated. This systematic approach results in the assembly of an ensemble of binary classifiers arranged sequentially, spanning from binary classifier level 4 to binary classifier level 12, with level 13 representing the pinnacle of difficulty.

5. Experimentation

This section describes the experiments conducted in this study. First, an overview of the dataset used for the analysis is provided. Subsequently, the data processing techniques employed are presented. Finally, the obtained results are presented, followed by a discussion and analysis of the findings.

5.1. Dataset

For the experiments, we use MoonBoard’s official website (MoonBoard, 2023). Starting from its initial configuration, each sample is introduced into the representation space transformation pipeline, as detailed in the previous sections. To estimate the accuracy of each model we design, we use the holdout strategy, which saves 30% of the samples for testing and the remainder for the training process.

Note that this public dataset is updated by all users who use the application. Any user can add a route and rate its difficulty. As mentioned, the rating of the difficulty of a climbing route is complex and depends on the user’s experience. Therefore, it is logical to assume that the dataset may be somewhat noisy (e.g., errors in estimating the difficulty of a route, errors related to the user’s experience, and even possible manual errors when entering the route into the application). However, in this work, it was chosen since it is a de facto standard in the field of climbing.

5.2. Results and discussion

This section presents and discusses the results obtained in the experiments. The development of the route classifier is based on the random forest algorithm (Breiman, 2001). It is an ML technique based on an ensemble of decision trees combined with bagging.

Two strategies were used in the experiments:

Fig. 7. Replication and transformation of the original dataset.

Fig. 8. Cascade Classifier Ensemble architecture. The ensemble starts by evaluating whether a climbing route is greater than level $V4$. If so, it checks the next level ($V5$). As long as the output of the binary model is positive, it continues with the higher level. Otherwise, it is assigned the level under evaluation.

1. “Multiclass”: This strategy involves the development of a multiclass classifier that can determine the appropriate difficulty level to assign based on an input escalation path. The objective is to construct a single classifier capable of accurately predicting the difficulty of a climbing route based on the provided information.
2. “Cascade”: This strategy refers to the architecture of classifier ensembles proposed in our work (CCE).

To estimate the classification error, we utilize the out-of-bag (OOB) error rate. In random forest models, this metric provides an average error estimation by employing the samples that were excluded from the bootstrap examples within a specific decision tree. These samples were not utilized during the training process and can therefore be used to estimate the model error. By leveraging the OOB samples, we can assess the error generated by the model.

Table 7 presents the confusion matrix for the “Multiclass” model. The analysis reveals that the model performance is not particularly satisfactory for routes of high difficulty (above $V9$). This finding can be attributed to the limited availability of samples for these specific difficulty levels. However, an average accuracy of 0.5 is achieved, which is slightly higher than the baseline accuracy of 0.42 versus (human expert), with which we conducted our comparison.

Furthermore, we present the results of the confusion matrices for the “Cascade” classifier. In this case, a separate confusion matrix is available for each classification level, which assesses the performance of classifying climbing routes of a specific level or higher (see Table 8).

The results demonstrate a significant improvement in performance achieved by the proposed “Cascade” classifier (CCE) compared to the “Multiclass” classifier. This improvement is evident even for higher difficulty levels, including those with limited sample sizes. In Fig. 9, the residual histograms are presented for the “Multiclass” classifier (Fig. 9(a)) and the CCE classifier (Fig. 9(b)). In the case of the CCE classifier, the histogram is computed by accumulating the values of the residual histograms from all binary classifiers. The error variance is slightly higher for the “Cascade” classifier, 0.21, than for the “Multiclass” classifier, 0.16, but its error is less biased. The mean and median residuals for the ‘Multiclass’ classifier are 0.32 and 0.34 respectively, while for the “Cascade” classifier, the mean is 0.004, and the median is -0.02 . A small increase in error variance is justified by the large decrease in bias. The histogram of the “Cascade” classifier is multimodal because this classifier is created by sequentially adding several binary classifiers.

Table 7
Confusion matrix of the “Multiclass” classifier.

		ACTUAL										
		V4	V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11	V12	V13	
PREDICTION	V4	6931	2554	407	151	87	17	5	3	0	0	
	V5	1893	3815	1807	988	742	150	41	7	2	0	
	V6	98	382	423	308	300	54	19	5	1	1	
	V7	24	104	199	243	235	39	16	5	1	2	
	V8	73	198	382	534	1049	424	159	58	12	8	
	V9	2	2	3	14	44	27	10	6	0	0	
	V10	0	0	0	0	3	4	12	0	0	0	
	V11	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	7	1	0	
	V12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	
	V13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 8
“Cascade” classifier confusion matrices. Each confusion matrix shows the performance of classifying a route at or above a certain level.

		V4	>V4			V5	>V5			V6	>V6
V4	5897	1596	V5	4842	1669	V6	1180	766			
>V4	3125	14477	>V5	2213	7349	>V6	2041	5031			

		V7	>V7			V8	>V8			V9	>V9
V7	809	568	V8	2252	853	V9	592	267			
>V7	1430	2990	>V8	208	245	>V9	124	115			

		V10	>V10			V11	>V11			V12	V13
V10	227	86	V11	83	24	V12	11	9			
>V10	35	34	>V11	9	4	V13	5	2			

Fig. 9. Histograms of the residuals for both classifiers are presented. The CCE classifier represents the cumulative value of all residuals from the binary classifiers.

Table 9
Results obtained with the three models: Human Classifier and the two models proposed in our work using the representation space transformation pipeline.

	Accuracy
Human Classifier	0.42
“Multiclass” Classifier	0.50
“Cascade” Classifier	0.63

Table 9 provides a summary of the accuracy in classifying climbing routes by difficulty, comparing the human model with our proposed models. The first multiclass model (“Multiclass”) utilizing the representation space transformation pipeline outperforms the human classifier.

The determination of the classification model’s accuracy is straightforward when considering the full “Multiclass” classifier: it corresponds to the proportion of correctly classified instances (sum of the diagonal) divided by the total number of instances. Conversely, for the “Cascade” classifier, individual confusion matrices are generated for each level. To

compute the accuracy of the “Cascade” classifier, the correct classifications across all levels are summed and then divided by the total number of instances. The resulting accuracy is 0.63.

In a levelling problem, understanding the criteria that govern the transition from one level to another is crucial. Specifically, in our context, it is valuable to identify the handholds that are most relevant for considering a route of a given or higher level of difficulty. The architecture of our proposed CCE classifier provides us with the ability to analyse and identify the most influential handholds to progress from a given difficulty level to a higher level. This analysis allows us to gain insight into the key factors that drive the increase in difficulty within our climbing route classification framework.

As previously mentioned, the CCE classifier is composed of an ensemble of classifiers using the random forest (RF) algorithm, which utilizes the decision tree bagging technique. It is widely recognized that decision tree splitting criteria introduce certain biases (Novakovic, 2010; Jr, 2001; Mohammad, 2018). These criteria, which are heuristics used to select the most relevant attributes, differ in their approach and emphasize various aspects of the attributes. Analysing these differences can shed light on both the obtained model and the underlying relationships between attributes.

Table 10

The table displays the attributes (handholds) that rank in the top 20% according to the three attribute selection measures (IG, GR, and SU) for the model obtained for all classes (“Multiclass”).

	“Multiclass”		
	IG	GR	SU
A3	0.0118	0.0560	0.0130
A8	0.0142	0.0715	0.0157
A26	0.0087	0.0657	0.0100
A29	0.0070	0.1192	0.0084
A38	0.0487	0.1042	0.0469
A41	0.0076	0.1588	0.0092
A62	0.0610	0.1409	0.0598
A84	0.0089	0.0633	0.0102
A93	0.0256	0.0722	0.0261
A96	0.0547	0.1142	0.0524
A104	0.0078	0.0636	0.0090
A115	0.0244	0.0579	0.0240
A128	0.0086	0.1072	0.0102
A149	0.0794	0.0922	0.0643
A156	0.0122	0.0743	0.0138
A169	0.0130	0.0638	0.0143

To compare features, three feature selection measures are used (Vasan K and B, 2017): information gain (IG), gain ratio (GR), and symmetrical uncertainty (SU). These measures identify the attributes that are most relevant to class prediction. The objective is to demonstrate that the two constructed models are distinct because they consider slightly different attributes to be important. This disparity suggests that the global model fails to incorporate attributes that are crucial for distinguishing between all classes, thus explaining the significant difference in results between the two models.

We apply these measures to the two models to determine whether there are differences in the importance of the attributes used for classification.

Table 10 shows the attributes (handholds) that are in the top 20% for the three measures IG, GR and SU for the model obtained for all classes (“Multiclass”). Tables 11 and 12 show some of the models that classify class X or higher (labelled VX/>VX).

The attributes (handholds) that are exclusively utilized in that model are indicated in green. For “Multiclass”, the most significant attributes are arguably the minimum common denominator of the most relevant attributes in the specific models. In contrast, other models possess attributes that are specific to them (highlighted in green), which could account for the improved performance of the “Cascade” model compared to the “Multiclass” model. Thus, the proposed architecture (CCE) provides climbers with an explanation of the most relevant attributes (handholds) for transitioning between difficulty levels. In addition, this model is designed for use in a collaborative environment, allowing climbers to contribute new routes with their respective difficulty ratings. The advantage of the CCE architecture is that retraining is required only for classifiers at the introduced level and those at lower levels, thereby eliminating the need to retrain all models.

To validate these results, individual conditional expectation (ICE) plots (Goldstein et al., 2015) for handholds deemed relevant for the binary classification V4/>V4 are presented in Fig. 10(a) (refer to Table 11 for handholds A149, A62, and A96). Additionally, corresponding plots for the handholds considered irrelevant for the same binary classification are depicted in Fig. 10(b). The ICE of a feature is derived by keeping the values of all other features constant and generating variations of the instance by substituting the value of the specific feature with the values it can assume. Subsequently, predictions are generated using the black-box model for these newly created instances. The outcome is a set of points representing the instance with the feature’s varied values alongside the corresponding predictions. The average of all created instances is then indicated with a thicker line. Consequently, the handholds considered more relevant for the binary

model V4/>V4 exhibit a distinctive prediction for each potential value of this handhold (see Fig. 10(a)). Conversely, handholds considered nonrelevant for calculating the difficulty of a route demonstrate a nearly constant prediction (see Fig. 10(b)). Identifying the most important handholds to classify the difficulty of routes leads to a better estimation of the difficulty when designing a new route.

6. Conclusions

This paper introduces a novel pipeline of representation space transformations for classifying the difficulty of climbing routes. The pipeline incorporates expert knowledge to enhance the performance of existing models. Furthermore, we propose an architecture based on an ensemble of cascade classifiers (CCE) that surpasses the performance of the single “Multiclass” classifier for all classes. The CCE model not only achieves higher accuracy than human classifiers in classifying MoonBoard climbing routes by difficulty but also provides valuable insights into the factors influencing the increase in difficulty level.

Our approach enables the analysis of key elements of climbing routes that determine their classification into specific levels of difficulty. This explanatory capacity is particularly valuable in levelling problems, as demonstrated in this study, as it sheds light on the most influential handholds that contribute to the difficulty level of a route during climbing route scaling. For a climber, having this type of detailed information is useful to facilitate strategic planning of a climb. A precise understanding of the available handholds empowers the climber to identify the most challenging sections, make necessary adjustments to their body position, and efficiently manage the effort required to overcome these segments. Additionally, this information offers climbers insight into the overall significance of the route, allowing them to evaluate the pivotal pitches that determine the difficulty level of a route.

In the present study, a sequence of representation space transformations was employed to assess the difficulty of climbing routes on a MoonBoard, which originated from an initial grid representation of a route. While the obtained results show promise, forthcoming investigations will explore the integration of additional approaches to enhance classification outcomes. Specifically, we will focus on the following areas:

- **Incorporation of Physiological Data:** We propose the integration of physiological data derived from wearable devices, such as fatigue levels, heart rate, and muscle activation, into the classification model. This integration will enable a more holistic understanding of a climber’s physical state and how it impacts route difficulty.
- **Behavioural Analysis:** Future work will examine climber behaviour metrics, including the number of route attempts, number of resting points, and climbing style. By analysing these factors, we aim to refine our model’s accuracy in predicting route difficulty based on behavioural patterns.
- **Autonomous Route Generation:** We plan to develop an algorithm capable of autonomously generating MoonBoard climbing routes for predefined difficulty grades. This algorithm will randomly generate routes adhering to predefined rules and constraints, and our classification model will validate the difficulty grade until a route matching the desired grade is identified.
- **Cross-Platform Application:** To extend the applicability of our methodology, we will adapt our models for use with other training boards, such as the KilterBoard and TensionBoard. This modification will involve replicating our methodology on these boards, incorporating their specific layout and handhold configurations. By doing so, we aim to facilitate the accurate classification of climbing routes across various platforms.

Table 11

This table displays the attributes (handholds) that rank in the top 20% according to the three attribute selection measures (IG, GR, and SU) for the model obtained for classes V4 ($V4 / > V4$) and V5 ($V5 / > V5$).

V4 / >V4				V5 / >V5			
	IG	GR	SU		IG	GR	SU
A3	0.008	0.037	0.018	A27	0.001	0.005	0.003
A8	0.009	0.044	0.021	A29	0.001	0.013	0.002
A26	0.006	0.042	0.014	A38	0.001	0.002	0.002
A31	0.008	0.033	0.017	A40	0.001	0.003	0.002
A38	0.038	0.081	0.068	A41	0.002	0.032	0.005
A39	0.009	0.035	0.019	A54	0.001	0.018	0.003
A59	0.006	0.046	0.015	A58	0.001	0.002	0.001
A62	0.056	0.129	0.103	A62	0.006	0.014	0.012
A84	0.006	0.041	0.015	A71	0.001	0.002	0.001
A93	0.021	0.060	0.042	A79	0.001	0.004	0.001
A96	0.043	0.091	0.077	A93	0.001	0.003	0.002
A104	0.004	0.036	0.011	A96	0.001	0.002	0.002
A115	0.015	0.035	0.027	A102	0.001	0.015	0.003
A128	0.004	0.049	0.011	A108	0.001	0.007	0.002
A136	0.005	0.037	0.013	A112	0.001	0.004	0.002
A149	0.061	0.071	0.081	A114	0.001	0.008	0.002
A156	0.008	0.049	0.020	A119	0.001	0.027	0.003
A169	0.008	0.038	0.018	A124	0.001	0.003	0.002
				A128	0.001	0.014	0.003
				A129	0.001	0.016	0.002
				A149	0.001	0.002	0.002

Table 12

This table displays the attributes (handholds) that rank in the top 20% according to the three attribute selection measures (IG, GR, and SU) for the model obtained for classes V6 ($V6 / > V6$) and V7 ($V7 / > V7$).

V6 / >V6				V7 / >V7			
	IG	GR	SU		IG	GR	SU
A8	0.002	0.009	0.007	A3	0.002	0.011	0.009
A26	0.001	0.009	0.006	A8	0.003	0.014	0.011
A31	0.001	0.005	0.004	A26	0.002	0.014	0.008
A38	0.006	0.014	0.017	A38	0.010	0.021	0.025
A52	0.001	0.006	0.005	A41	0.002	0.043	0.011
A60	0.003	0.008	0.008	A50	0.003	0.011	0.011
A62	0.007	0.016	0.019	A60	0.004	0.012	0.013
A69	0.001	0.009	0.005	A62	0.009	0.021	0.024
A84	0.001	0.007	0.005	A84	0.002	0.013	0.008
A93	0.003	0.01	0.01	A93	0.005	0.014	0.015
A96	0.007	0.014	0.017	A96	0.011	0.023	0.027
A115	0.003	0.007	0.008	A102	0.002	0.024	0.009
A120	0.003	0.008	0.008	A104	0.002	0.017	0.009
A149	0.01	0.012	0.017	A114	0.002	0.028	0.010
A156	0.001	0.007	0.005	A115	0.007	0.017	0.019
A169	0.001	0.006	0.005	A120	0.006	0.018	0.018
				A128	0.002	0.029	0.012
				A136	0.002	0.013	0.008
				A138	0.002	0.020	0.009
				A149	0.017	0.020	0.029
				A156	0.002	0.015	0.010
				A169	0.003	0.014	0.011

The main objective of this paper is to introduce a methodology for assessing the difficulty of climbing routes, accompanied by interpretable insights into the reasons why they are classified as having a specific degree of difficulty. Although the focus of this study is the MoonBoard, the methodology can be applied to other training boards, such as the KilterBoard or TensionBoard. These training boards typically have associated applications that allow climbers to access routes of varying difficulty levels and even input their own routes. Each training board follows a standardized layout, enabling climbers worldwide to query routes by difficulty using the same board. To replicate this methodology, experienced climbers assessed the difficulty of the handholds. Once the new grading system is established, non-expert users can input new routes, and the system can indicate the degree of difficulty of the route. Consequently, in future research, we will aim to extend the development of climbing route classification models to accommodate other platforms that offer similar services, such as KilterBoard or TensionBoard. By broadening the application

of our models, we aspire to contribute to the accurate classification of climbing routes across various platforms.

In recent years, new large language models with image recognition capabilities, known as Visual Language Models (Zhang et al., 2024), including those capable of recognizing human activities, have emerged. These models enable a variety of functionalities, from analysing the context of traffic images (de Zarzà et al., 2023) to performing symbolic reasoning (Wu et al., 2024). Future work will involve the integration of these models, either by replacing the dynamic information provided by BetaMove or by developing a metamodel through stacking ensemble techniques.

In summary, the work conducted in this study opens exciting possibilities for future research. Beyond enabling a more precise generation of climbing routes based on specific grades, this work makes a valuable contribution by offering interpretability regarding the relevance of handholds in climbing routes.

Fig. 10. ICE plots of various handholds are presented for the binary classifier V4/>V4. For a specific route, additional routes are generated while maintaining the other handholds at constant values. Each new route corresponds to the potential values that the specific handhold, for which the ICE is being obtained, can assume. The thicker line represents the average output of the binary classifier V4/>V4.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Miguel A. Patricio: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nicolás Granados:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **José M. Molina:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Antonio Berlanga:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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